

Evaluation and comparison of pre-trained convolutional neural networks for detecting Equine Pain Face

(Christiansen et al., 2021)

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Preface

The aim of this project is looking into seven pre-trained models to evaluate their image classification performance on horses with “pain face” and “no pain face”. It has been written to fulfil the graduation of a bachelor’s in science in animal science at the University of Copenhagen. It is written as an original article to be subjected for publishing in the journal Equine Veterinary.

Together with our supervisor, Dan Børge Jensen, the aim of the project was formulated. Dan Børge Jensen supervised the project, especially with machine learning and statistical analysis. In correspondence with our co-supervisor, Christina Larsen, we got supervised through the introduction and discussion. A special thanks to our supervisor, Dan Børge Jensen, for all the meetings, your endless patience when teaching us about machine learning concepts, and every time we nearly gave up on R. We could not have done this without you. Thanks to our co-supervisor, Christina Larsen, for always boosting our self-confidence and advising us on the writing and the defence. Thank you to Lea Schønberg Olsen for converting the videos into images, cropping the images, and making our dataset ready.

We would also like to thank Franziska Hakansson and Dan Børge Jensen for letting us participate in their research project on detecting pain faces in horses. This project is relevant and addresses an important problem that needs more attention.

We hope you will find this study interesting and useful. Maybe even inspire you to participate in this field of horse welfare.

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Abstract

Background: The welfare of sports and ridden horses is a growing concern as pain behaviour in horses is often misinterpreted as conflict behaviour. As prey animals, horses tend to suppress their pain signs against possible predators. The Equine Pain Face (EPF) evaluation identifies pain through facial expressions but is subjective due to varying observer assessments.

The aim: This study aims to develop an artificial intelligence model to detect “pain face” or “no pain face” in horses to solve this issue. Performances of seven pre-trained base-models were evaluated and compared: *VGG16*, *Xception*, *DenseNet201*, *ResNet101V2*, *MobileNetV2*, *EfficientNetB7*, and *InceptionResNetV2*, using a dataset of 613 images.

Study design/methodology: To secure the best and most reliable performance possible, the hyperparameters, principal components and hidden factors were systematically varied, and cross-validation was utilised. The area under the ROC curve (AUC) was used to measure said performance.

Results: All models achieved an AUC between 0.95-0.99, with *DenseNet201* and *Xception* reaching 0.99. The findings highlight the importance of optimising hyperparameters to avoid random guess-like results, as seen with the worst performances of *VGG16* and *MobileNetV2*. The study’s results are discussed and compared to existing research in the scientific field.

Main limitations: Encoding and training times were constrained by computer capacity, with deeper models like *InceptionResNetV2* requiring more time, underscoring the need for adequate computational resources for training deep models.

Conclusion: To select the most suitable model to detect pain faces in horses depends on computer capacity and time available. *DenseNet201* is recommended if the computer capacity is unlimited. *VGG16* is suitable for limited capacity.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, Equine Pain Face, horse welfare, machine learning, model evaluation.

1. Introduction

Welfare among horses, especially sports and ridden horses, is an increasing concern worldwide (Ladewig et al., 2022). The training methods are often similar to those used when horses were domesticated and did not incorporate welfare (Waran et al., 2007). Pain can, for that reason, be unseen. The expressions of pain from the behavioural responses of the horse are often misunderstood while ridden and training the horse (Ladewig et al., 2022). It can be musculoskeletal, tack-induced, or rider-induced pain caused by the rider's rein, legs, or body weight (Dyson et al., 2018). These behavioural responses from the horse during the riding session are often referred to as conflict behaviours resulting from unclear cues from the rider (Hamilton et al., 2022) and not as pain behaviour signs.

1.1 Equine Pain Face

Pain is a subjective emotional experience (Gleerup & Lindegaard, 2016). Because horses and humans do not communicate verbally, it can be challenging to observe and predict the power and location of pain in horses. Horses are, by nature, herbivores and are considered prey species. Prey species, and therefore horses in this context, may be able to suppress their pain and hide their signs in the presence of humans as possible predators (Dalla Costa et al., 2014). Therefore, it is essential to examine normal equine behaviour to identify changes in behaviour related to pain. The Equine Pain Face (EPF) evaluation can be used for this purpose.

Facial expressions related to pain cannot be suppressed entirely. Therefore, pain in horses can be spotted in their facial expressions. The pain features of the equine facial expression in the EPF are (1) low ears, where the distance between the ears becomes larger, (2) angled eyes, where the muscles surrounding the eyes are tensed, (3) tense stare, (4) nostrils strained, where it changes from a normal to a square marked shape. (5) muzzle tension around the mouth and chin, and (6) tension of the mimic muscles in the face, especially the jaw muscles (Gleerup & Lindegaard, 2016).

The Equine Pain Scale (EPS), published by Gleerup & Lindegaard (2016), is primarily used in veterinarian hospitals to observe common pain behaviours in horses. The EPF is incorporated into the behaviour categories.

The sheet used to evaluate equine pain has nine different behaviour categories, each with a score from 0-4, and should be observed multiple times a day. The behaviour categories are “pain face”, “gross pain behaviour”, “activity”, “location in the stall”, “posture/weight

bearing”, “head position”, “attention toward a painful area”, “interactive behaviour” and “response to food” (Gleerup et al., 2021). After performing and filling out the nine categories in the EPS sheet, the final pain score can be summed up to a number/score between 0 and 30 (Gleerup et al., 2021).

The use of EPF is subjective, as different observers may have varying interpretations of a horse’s pain face, making it challenging to quantify consistently. To address this issue, it is pertinent to develop an artificial intelligence (AI) system for image classification to detect the presence of “pain” or “no pain” faces in horses. An AI would provide an objective and consistent evaluation, making quantifying the EPF assessment easier.

1.2 Machine Learning

Machine learning is the basis of artificial intelligence. It refers to a class of algorithms that develop models for classification and prediction by analysing existing data rather than relying on explicit instructions. The computer learns from past experiences to enhance its performance over time (Cohen, 2020). Machine learning revolves around concept learning. Concept learning involves understanding general rules or patterns from a given set of examples. These are then used to predict or classify new instances (Cohen, 2020). Machine learning algorithms learn to make sense of data by identifying patterns and correlations used to make predictions (Cohen, 2020).

Convolutional networks (CNN) are artificial neural networks designed for tasks involving images and spatial data. It is called “convolutional” since it uses convolutional layers to process the input data (Manaswi, 2018). CNN is a deep, feed-forward network that consists of multiple layers, allowing it to learn complex patterns and hierarchies of features (Manaswi, 2018). CNNs learn to extract features from images hierarchically, where lower layers detect simple features like edges and textures, and higher layers combine these features to recognise more complex patterns like shapes and objects (Manaswi, 2018).

CNNs are adept at generalising learned features to new, unseen data. This means that even if the network is trained on a specific data set, it can still recognise similar patterns in new images it has not encountered before (Manaswi, 2018). CNNs are commonly used for various image-related tasks, such as object recognition and image classification (Manaswi, 2018), which we use for this study. In our study, we have chosen seven pre-trained base models to do image

classification on horses with or without pain faces. The pre-trained models have been used and researched in different image classification studies. The overall accuracy of all the models is satisfactory, and we would like to use the following base models in our research.

VGG16 has been used to classify images of two species, dogs and cats, so there are two classes. In this study, with fine-tuned image augmentation, *VGG16* was accurate at 95.40% (Tammina, 2019).

During Covid-19, one of the prevention methods against coronavirus transmission was the use of masks. *Densenet201* was used to identify masked or non-masked faces in that context (Dharma Adhinata et al., 2021). *Densenet201* has an F-measure value of 0.98 (Dharma Adhinata et al., 2021).

MobileNetV2 has been tested on two datasets from TensorFlow to evaluate its accuracy. The first dataset is “Colorectal histology,” which contains textures in colorectal cancer histology, and the second one is “Eurosat,” which contains geo-referenced samples. The test accuracy of *MobileNetV2* in this study is 89 % (Dong et al., 2020).

Xception was used for image classification in six different garbage classes where transfer learning methods were used. The results show that *Xception* got a higher accuracy than *VGG16* in this study for this classification of 88% (Rismiyati et al., 2020).

InceptionResNetV2 has been used for image classification in breast cancer histology (Ferreira et al., 2018), and it looks like the study with *MobileNetV2* above. There were four classes of images to classify: normal tissue, benign abnormality, malignant in situ carcinoma, and malignant invasive carcinoma (Ferreira et al., 2018). *InceptionResNetV2* has a test accuracy of 90 % (Ferreira et al., 2018).

Brain tumour images are another cancer image classification, and *EfficientNetB7* has been used for this purpose. The dataset is divided into three classes depending on the type of brain tumour: meningiomas, gliomas, and pituitary. *EfficientNetB7* has an accuracy of 95% (Purnama Wibowo et al., 2022).

ResNet101V2 has been used to classify Alzheimer’s disease (AD) from Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) images of the brain (Saiful et al., 2023). In this study, *ResNet101V2*’s accuracy is 98.35% (Saiful et al., 2023).

This study aims to train artificial intelligence models to detect the Equine Pain Face (EPF) on images of horses. We can access seven existing pre-trained base-models to recognise objects within 1000 categories. The objective of this project is to identify the most suitable model to pre-process the images for EPF evaluation, which leads to our problem statement: How can we select the most suitable model among the seven existing pre-trained base-models to pre-process images of horses for Equine Pain Face (EPF) evaluation?

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Data source

Casper Lindegaard provided the data used in this study from the Large Animals Hospital in Taastrup, Denmark. The data consists of 22 videos of 11 horses, recorded before and after surgery for Equine odontoclastic tooth resorption and hypercementosis (EOTRH) (Bach, 2020). These videos were annotated by Karina Glerup from veterinary Karina Bech Glerup ApS on the address Elleorevej 9, 4000 Roskilde, Veddelev, in terms of which videos showed EPF and which videos did not.

Eleven videos show horses expressing “pain face”, and eleven videos show the same horses not expressing pain face as “no pain face”. Anne Bach Bjarre filmed the horses in their own stable environment. The length of the videos varies from 9.96 to 30.96 seconds, equivalent to the time the horse spends eating a carrot (Bach, 2020). Some videos are filmed vertically in portrait, and others are filmed horizontally in landscape, as shown in Tables 1 and 2.

2.2 Video pre-processing

The images were extracted from the videos through the program FFMPEG (Tomar, 2006). The command used was as follows:

```
ffmpeg -i [Video#].mp4 -qscale:v 2 -r 1 pain/nopain_[video#]_1_%2d.png
```

In this command, ‘ffmpeg’ calls upon the program. The ‘-i’ defines which input file should be processed, where [Video#] refers to the video number of each video. The image quality is prioritised over a small file size by setting the ‘qscale:v’ to 2. The ‘-r 1’ sets the extraction rate

of the images to one frame per second. Lastly, the command names the output files based on the video number of the input file (FFMPEG, 2024).

The images were then cropped using the R shiny application ImageCropping (D. Jensen, 2024) to achieve uniformity. The black borders were removed from the vertically filmed images, and the horizontally filmed images were cropped to match the same format. The images were simultaneously centred on the horse's face when this procedure was completed.

The inclusion criteria for the images were as follows: the face of the horse had to be in the frame and not occluded in the frame. Additionally, the image could not be so blurry as to obscure the facial features.

The full dataset consisted of 613 images, 316 showing horses expressing a "pain face" and 297 presenting a "no pain face."

To encode our data to our base models and train and test some of the secondary models, we used a MacBook Pro, M1, 2020, with 8 CPU cores, whereas we used 6 CPU cores. Additionally, the laptop has 8 GB RAM, the GPU "Intel Iris Plus Graphics 655", and 16GB of dedicated memory. To train and test the deepest secondary models, we used a desktop computer running Windows 10 with 8 CPU cores, 128 GB of RAM, and an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090 GPU with 24 GB of dedicated memory.

2.3 Implementation

In this study, the software used to implement the algorithms was R version 4.3.3 and the library "Keras" (Version 2.13.0). We used data augmentation, where each original image was copied 24 times, where every copy was varied randomly in brightness between -0.15 and 0.15, contrast between 0.8 and 2, rotation between -20 and 20 degrees, and flipping the image horizontally or not. We used each original image extracted from the videos, all titled 0. Data augmentation helps the model acquire more resilient features that effectively generalise to new, unseen data by generating fresh, modified versions of the existing data (Nanthini et al., 2023).

The images were converted and resized to 224×224 pixels in resolution to fit the input size of the base model's networks. 20% of our data were randomly labelled as a validation set as a separated subset to do cross-validation.

Figure 1: Flowchart of methodology for one of the base models. Here is the example of VGG16.

2.4 Processing base models

We are creating a data frame of vectors from our images with seven base models, as listed below:

Table 1: Showing the base model and its sizes, top-1 accuracy, top-5 accuracy, parameters and depth

Model	Size (MB)	Top-1 Accuracy (%)	Top-5 Accuracy (%)	Parameters (M)	Depth	References:
VGG16	528	71.3	90.1	138.4	16	(Simonyan & Zisserman, 2014)
Xception	88	79	94.5	22.9	81	(Chollet, 2016)
DenseNet201	80	77.3	93.6	20.2	402	(Huang et al., 2016)
InceptionResNetV2	215	80.3	95.3	55.9	449	(Szegedy et al., 2017)
ResNet101V2	171	77.2	93.8	44.7	205	(He et al., 2016)
MobileNetV2	14	71.3	90.1	3.5	105	(Sandler et al., 2018)
EfficientNetB7	256	84.3	97	66.7	438	(Tan & Le, 2019)

We chose the base-models above out of nine families, testing the best from each. We ended with seven models because two base-models did not exist in the R-package “Keras.” Previous studies have shown satisfying results with similar image classification studies of these seven base-models.

Images from the videos with a “pain face” are categorised as 1, and images with “no pain face” are categorised as 0. All metadata has been removed to ensure that the secondary models cannot recognise "pain face" based on filenames, which are labelled as either "pain" or "no pain." To reduce the workload, we found the variance for each feature for each video. Then, we found the minimum variance for each feature for any given video. We identify the features where the minimum variance is 0, which is the features that have a variance of 0 for at least one video. These will be the features we remove to create a new data frame of vectors, which was our training set.

2.5 Secondary models

Training and making a fully connected (artificial) neural network (FC-ANN) requires different parameters. It depends on the number of principal components (N_{PC}) we use, which informs us about the size of the input vector. PC Analysis (PCA) finds patterns and trends in the dataset and transforms them into summaries of features (Lever et al., 2017). PCAs reduce the data by projecting them into principal components (PC) (Lever et al., 2017). This study used N_{PC} of 32, 64, 128, 256, 512, and 9999999, which are the most effective according to previous studies (Jensen et al.). Therefore, N_{PC} 2, 4, 8, 16, and 1024 were distracted.

2.6 Cross-validation

80% of the images would then be divided into a training set and 20% into a validation set for cross-validation. Validation sets were employed to evaluate the model's adequacy during training, whereas test sets were utilised to assess the model's ability to make predictions on a new (unseen) dataset.

To balance our data, we used “undersampling” to decrease the overrepresentation of any category in the training set. Data balancing was not used in the validation and test sets.

2.7 Creating FC-ANN Architecture

After creating all three sets, a training set, a test set and a validation set, we created the FC-ANN architecture. An FC-ANN architecture consists of input and the number of hidden layers used in the network. Our network consists of one hidden layer since one hidden layer can learn any connection if there is a connecting line (Brightwell, 1996). Based on previous studies, the

hidden factors ($N_{\text{Hidden_factor}}$) in our network's hidden layer are 2/3, 1, or 4/3 (Larsen et al., 2019) to help learn different patterns in the dataset. The ReLu activation function is used for this specific step.

Furthermore, we follow the example of Srivastava et al. (2014), with a dropout rate of 20% in the input layer and 50% in the hidden layer. Dropout rates randomly choose nodes in the hidden layer, where connections are set equal to 0. During training, the model must use data from different perspectives to reduce overfitting. A batch size of 64 is used during training, which is the number of observations the model goes through in the training set.

2.8 Training and testing secondary model

Before training, we want to compile our models. We are training them for a maximum of 200 epochs with a learning rate of 0.001 using the loss function optimiser Adam. Additionally, binary cross-entropy loss is used. We use early stopping with a patience of 5, which is the number of epochs we wait before we accept that the model is no longer improving. After each epoch, the training model is applied to the validation set, validating the data. Patience tells us that when the validation has not improved after five epochs, it settles with the best model before the early stopping.

In this study, we aim to systematically vary in N_{PC} and $N_{\text{Hidden_factor}}$ to find the most efficient model.

2.9 Performance evaluation

The area under the ROC curve (AUC) is used as a performance measure. The ROC curve plots sensitivity against 1-specificity for different threshold values used to classify the data. The AUC provides a single scalar value representing the model's overall performance across all possible threshold values. $AUC = 1$ indicates a perfect discriminator that achieves ideal sensitivity and specificity, and an AUC over 0.80 is considered valid, whereas $AUC = 0.5$ is as good as random guessing. (Çorbacioğlu & Aksel, 2023). The 'auc' function of the 'MESS' library in R was used to calculate AUC.

$$\text{Sensitivity} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{TN}{TN + FP} \quad (2)$$

A true positive (TP) is when the FC-ANN correctly identifies when a “pain face” is expressed, a true negative (TN) is when the FC-ANN correctly identifies when “no pain face” is expressed, a false negative (FN) is when the FC-ANN wrongly identifies a “pain face” as “no pain face”, a false positive (FP) is when the FC-ANN wrongly identifies “no pain face” as a “pain face”. In this study, the sensitivity (SE) measures the proportion of “pain face” expressions correctly identified, while the specificity (SP) measures the proportion of “no pain face” expressions correctly identified.

Trainable parameters for the best and worst secondary models are extracted with the equations as follows:

$$\text{Trainable parameters} = (N_{PC} + \text{bias}) \cdot (N_{PC} \cdot N_{\text{hidden_factor}}) \cdot N_{\text{out}} \quad (3)$$

In our neural network, we have a bias node in the input layer and the hidden layer. The bias node in both layers equals 1.

2.10 Confidence Intervals and P values

To find the CI and, afterwards, the p-values between samples A and B, we use the equations below. In our case, between the sensitivity and specificity for the naive and the best and worst secondary models, as well as between the AUC value for the best secondary models with lower N_{PC} and the best secondary models AUC value.

First, we found the shared standard error for models A and B, each of which has the estimated performance metric (i.e. AUC, sensitivity or specificity) and, respectively, with the equations below:

$$\text{StandardError_shared} = \sqrt{\text{StandardError}_A^2 + \text{StandardError}_B^2} \quad (4)$$

We subtracted B from A to find the estimated difference. An example could be the AUC values.

$$\text{EstDiff} = \text{AUC}_B - \text{AUC}_A \quad (5)$$

We want to find the upper and lower CI using the following equations:

$$\text{upr}_{\text{Diff}} = \text{EstDiff} + 1.96 \cdot \text{StandardError_shared} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{lwr}_{\text{Diff}} = \text{EstDiff} - 1.96 \cdot \text{StandardError_shared} \quad (7)$$

Then, we find the z-value.

$$z = \frac{EstDiff}{StandardError_shared} \quad (8)$$

P-values are then estimated using the `pnorm` function in R as follows:

$$p_{value} = 2 \cdot pnorm(-abs(z)) \quad (9)$$

To see how few NPC can be used as inputs in the secondary model with the same N_{hidden_factor} without the performance becoming significantly worse than for the secondary model, we found the p-values and lower and upper 95% CI with the method described above. Before finding the shared standard error for the AUCs between the best secondary models with lower NPC and the best secondary model, we calculated the standard error for both with the equations as follows, where 22 references to the number of videos:

$$StandardError_A = \sqrt{\frac{AUC_A \cdot (1 - AUC_A)}{22}} \quad (10)$$

$$StandardError_Best = \sqrt{\frac{AUC_{Best} \cdot (1 - AUC_{Best})}{22}} \quad (11)$$

To ensure that the best and worst secondary models did not simply learn to recognise if the images were filmed horizontally or vertically, we found the p-values and lower and upper 95% CI to be compared with the naive model for sensitivity and specificity.

There are 11 videos in each category of “pain face” and “no pain face”. To find the naive sensitivity (SE), we divided the five videos filmed horizontally into the ‘pain’ category, with all 11 videos in that category. Moreover, to find the naive specificity (SP), we divided the ten videos filmed vertically into the ‘no pain’ category, with all 11 videos in that category. Then, we found the standard error for SE and SP for both the best and worst secondary models and the naive models, and afterwards, find the shared standard error for SE and SP with the equations as follows:

$$\text{StandardErrorSE}_{\text{model}} = \sqrt{\frac{SE_{\text{model}} \cdot (1 - SE_{\text{model}})}{TP}} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{StandardErrorSP}_{\text{model}} = \sqrt{\frac{SP_{\text{model}} \cdot (1 - SP_{\text{model}})}{TN}} \quad (13)$$

$$\text{StandardErrorSE}_{\text{naive}} = \sqrt{\frac{SE_{\text{naive}} \cdot (1 - SE_{\text{naive}})}{TP}} \quad (14)$$

$$\text{StandardErrorSP}_{\text{naive}} = \sqrt{\frac{SP_{\text{naive}} \cdot (1 - SP_{\text{naive}})}{TN}} \quad (15)$$

2.11 Plots and bar charts

We are interested in researching whether there is a correlation between the best AUC and the seven different base-models' parameters, depth, and top-1 accuracy. We created a performance.best.all dataset for the various models. We then generated a linear regression that describes the best AUC given the base-models parameters and similarly with the depth and top-1 accuracy.

Then, we plotted the best AUCs on the y-axis and the parameters, depth, and top-1 accuracy on the x-axis to visualise the correlation. Furthermore, we have inserted the p-values and r^2 values for each correlation to show how much the parameters, depth, and top-1 accuracy influence the AUC and the significance probability.

Likewise, we made a linear regression that describes the worst AUC given the parameters, depth, and top-1 accuracy of the base-models to see if there is a connection between the worst AUC and the variables.

$$\begin{aligned} LM1 < -lm(AUC \sim Parameters + Depth + Top1Accuracy \\ + Top5Accuracy, data = performance.best.all) \end{aligned}$$

Finally, we made bar charts to compare the best and worst AUC values and the corresponding 95% confidence intervals for the different secondary models.

3. Results

3.1 Descriptive statistics

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics for each video, including whether the video represents a horse with “pain face” or “no pain face”, the number of the video, how it is filmed, the length of the video, the number of images, and discarded images.

Table 2: Showing the frame, length, number of images and discarded images for videos with pain and no pain

Pain/no pain	Video	Frame	Length (sec.)	Number of included images	Discarded images
Pain	5	Horizontal	29.93	32	0
Pain	22	Horizontal	30.96	33	0
Pain	8	Horizontal	30.89	33	0
Pain	11	Horizontal	26.56	27	1
Pain	9	Horizontal	9.96	11	0
Pain	20	Vertical	30.96	33	0
Pain	17	Vertical	30.96	33	0
Pain	15	Vertical	30.96	33	0
Pain	1	Vertical	30.96	32	1
Pain	6	Vertical	21.12	23	0
Pain	10	Vertical	30.96	32	1
No pain	4	Horizontal	30.84	22	10
No pain	18	Vertical	26.96	29	0
No pain	2	Vertical	3.96	6	0
No pain	13	Vertical	28.4	30	0
No pain	7	Vertical	30.96	33	0
No pain	21	Vertical	9.96	12	0
No pain	14	Vertical	30.96	32	1
No pain	3	Vertical	30.96	33	0
No pain	19	Vertical	30.96	33	0
No pain	12	Vertical	30.92	33	0
No pain	16	Vertical	30.8	31	1

Figure 2 shows a horse from our dataset with “pain face”, a horse with “no pain face”, and additionally, a discarded image is shown to illustrate that the horse's face is not available for the base-models to interpret.

Figure 2: Horse with (A) “pain face”, (B) “no pain face”, and (C) a discarded image.

Table 3 illustrates the encoding time in hours for the seven base-models. The encoding time refers to the time used for the base-models to convert the images from all videos to vectors. These base-models produced features from the data, and after removing features with a variance of 0, some features remained. This is depicted in Table 3 as well.

Table 3: The encoding time for the different base-models, the features produced, and the features left after removing features with a variance of 0

Base-models	Encoding time (hours)	Features produced	Remaining Features
VGG16	1.01	25088	736
Xception	2.7	100352	2499
DenseNet201	2.32	94080	15325
ResNet101V2	3.97	100352	10782
MobileNetV2	1.39	62720	11585
InceptionResNetV2	8.49	38400	12689
EfficientNetB7	11	125440	15325

Table 4 shows the best secondary models and their best AUC value, the N_{PC} used to get the best AUC value, and the N_{Hidden_factor}. Furthermore, it shows the sensitivity (SE), specificity (SP), true positive (TP), true negative (TN), false positive (FP) and false negative (FN) for the best secondary models.

Table 4: The best secondary models and their AUC value, N_{PC}, hidden factor, SE, SP, TP, TN, FP and FN.

Best secondary models	Best AUC	N_PC	N_Hidden_factor	SE	SP	TP	FP	TN	FN	Trainable parameters
VGG16	0.95	256	1	1	0.9	11	1	10	0	66048
Xception	0.99	2499	1	1	1	11	0	11	0	6249999
DenseNet201	0.99	128	1.33	1	1	11	0	11	0	22131
ResNet101V2	0.98	10782	0.67	1	1	11	0	11	0	77902969
MobileNetV2	0.98	256	0.67	1	1	11	0	11	0	44252
InceptionResNetV2	0.97	64	1	1	0.9	11	1	10	0	4224
EfficientNetB7	0.96	64	1	0.9	1	10	0	11	1	4224

Table 5 shows the worst secondary models and their worst AUC value, the PC used to get the worst AUC value and the hidden factors.

Table 5: The worst secondary models and their AUC value, N_{PC}, hidden factor, SE, SP, TP, TN, FP and FN.

Worst secondary models	Worst AUC	N_PC	N_Hidden factor	SE	SP	TP	FP	TN	FN	Trainable parameters
VGG16	0.68	32	0.67	0.8	0.5	9	5	6	2	729
Xception	0.78	32	1.33	0.8	0.7	9	3	8	2	1447
DenseNet201	0.78	32	0.67	0.8	0.8	9	2	9	2	729
ResNet101V2	0.75	32	0.67	0.9	0.6	10	4	7	1	729
MobileNetV2	0.7	32	1.33	0.8	0.7	9	3	8	2	1447
InceptionResNetV2	0.73	12689	1	0.8	0.6	9	4	7	2	161036099
EfficientNetB7	0.82	128	1	0.6	0.9	7	1	10	4	16640

Figure 3 shows the distributions (median, Q1-Q3) of the average estimated probability for the presence of a pain face in images from a video with “no pain face” (0) and the probability distribution for a pain face in videos with a “pain face” (1). The red dashed line at 0.5 represents a baseline. The greater the distance between the medians of the two distributions from this line, the better the model can be said to perform. The left column represents predictions of the best secondary models, and the right column represents predictions of the worst secondary models.

Figure 3: The distribution (median, Q1-Q3) of the predictions of the best (to the left) and worst (to the right) secondary models, given the ground truth state (0 = "no pain face", 1 = "pain face").

3.2 AUC and corresponding 95% CI

Figure 4 shows the best and worst AUCs with the corresponding 95% CI, as achieved with the secondary models for each of the seven base-models. The red line indicates the lowest AUC value performed by the secondary models, and the blue line indicates the best AUC. The black line is 0.5 AUC. Figure 4A shows the best AUC from the secondary models, and Figure 4B shows the worst AUC the secondary models performed.

Figure 4: Bar plot showing the best (A) and worst (B) AUC for the seven secondary models and the corresponding 95% confidence interval. The blue line refers to the highest-scoring AUC value, the red line refers to the lowest-scoring AUC value, and the black line is an AUC value of 0.5, which includes both A and B.

3.3 Linear regressions

Figure 5 shows six linear regressions. Figure 5A shows the best AUC given the parameters of the base-models, Figure 5B shows the best AUC given the depth of the base-models, and Figure 5C shows the best AUC given the top-1 accuracy of the base-models. Similarly, Figure 6 illustrates the same but with the models' worst AUC values. The figures also show p-values and r^2 values for each correlation.

Figure 5: Linear regression that describes the best and worst AUC, and (A) the parameters of the models, (B) the depth of the models and (C) the top1 accuracy of the models.

3.4 P-values

Table 6 shows p-values for sensitivity and specificity, comparing the seven best secondary models with the naive model. The naive model is the one that represents recognising horizontal and vertical images rather than recognising “pain face” and “no pain face”.

Table 6: *p*-values to compare the seven best secondary models with the naive model. NS = non-significant, = borderline significant and * = significant

Base-models	p-values		p-values	
	Sensitivity	Significance level for sensitivity	Specificity	Significance level for specificity
VGG16	0.0003	*	1	NS
Xception	0.0003	*	0.26	NS
DenseNet201	0.0003	*	0.26	NS
ResNet101V2	0.0003	*	0.26	NS
MobileNetV2	0.0003	*	0.26	NS
InceptionResNetV2	0.0003	*	1	NS
EfficientNetB7	0.0124	*	0.26	NS

Table 7 shows *p*-values for sensitivity and specificity, comparing the seven worst secondary models with the naive model.

Table 7: *p*-values to compare the seven worst secondary models with the naive model. NS = non-significant, = borderline significant and * = significant

Base-models	p-values		p-values	
	Sensitivity	Significance level for sensitivity	Specificity	Significance level for specificity
VGG16	0.083	.	0.12	NS
Xception	0.083	.	0.33	NS
DenseNet201	0.083	.	0.57	NS
ResNet101V2	0.012	*	0.2	NS
MobileNetV2	0.083	.	0.33	NS
InceptionResNetV2	0.083	.	0.2	NS
EfficientNetB7	0.48	NS	1	NS

Table 8 shows the differences between the best AUC and the AUCs obtained using lower N_{PC} (but the same N_{Hidden_factor}), as well as the *p*-values for these differences. The *p*-values indicate whether the differences are significantly different or not.

Table 8: *p*-values to compare the seven best secondary models AUC with their N_{PC} s and all the N_{PC} s underneath. NS = non-significant, =borderline significant and * = significant.

Base-model	Comparison	Difference	p-value	Confidence level
VGG16	AUC $N_{PC}=256$ -AUC $N_{PC}=32$	0.18	0.07	.
VGG16	AUC $N_{PC}=256$ -AUC $N_{PC}=64$	0.07	0.4	NS
VGG16	AUC $N_{PC}=256$ -AUC $N_{PC}=128$	0.05	0.53	NS
Xception	AUC $N_{PC}=2499$ -AUC $N_{PC}=32$	0.18	0.04	*
Xception	AUC $N_{PC}=2499$ -AUC $N_{PC}=64$	0.09	0.18	NS
Xception	AUC $N_{PC}=2499$ -AUC $N_{PC}=128$	0.08	0.22	NS
Xception	AUC $N_{PC}=2499$ -AUC $N_{PC}=256$	0.01	0.78	NS
Xception	AUC $N_{PC}=2499$ -AUC $N_{PC}=512$	0.03	0.52	NS
DenseNet201	AUC $N_{PC}=128$ -AUC $N_{PC}=32$	0.08	0.22	NS
DenseNet201	AUC $N_{PC}=128$ -AUC $N_{PC}=64$	0.03	0.52	NS
ResNet101V2	AUC $N_{PC}=10782$ -AUC $N_{PC}=32$	0.23	0.02	*
ResNet101V2	AUC $N_{PC}=10782$ -AUC $N_{PC}=64$	0.09	0.22	NS
ResNet101V2	AUC $N_{PC}=10782$ -AUC $N_{PC}=128$	0.08	0.26	NS
ResNet101V2	AUC $N_{PC}=10782$ -AUC $N_{PC}=256$	0.09	0.22	NS
ResNet101V2	AUC $N_{PC}=10782$ -AUC $N_{PC}=512$	0.03	0.59	NS
MobileNetV2	AUC $N_{PC}=256$ -AUC $N_{PC}=32$	0.25	0.01	*
MobileNetV2	AUC $N_{PC}=256$ -AUC $N_{PC}=64$	0.16	0.07	.
MobileNetV2	AUC $N_{PC}=256$ -AUC $N_{PC}=128$	0.09	0.22	NS
InceptionResNetV2	AUC $N_{PC}=64$ -AUC $N_{PC}=32$	0.07	0.34	NS
EfficientNetB7	AUC $N_{PC}=64$ -AUC $N_{PC}=32$	0.02	0.76	NS

4. Discussion

4.1 Evaluating the performance

In this study, we define the most suitable secondary model as achieving the highest AUC while remaining as simple as possible to minimise the risk of overfitting. The balance between performance and simplicity is a critical factor in the effectiveness of our secondary model. The first step in selecting the most suitable secondary model among the seven pre-trained base-models is identifying the secondary model with the highest AUC. If multiple secondary models achieve the same AUC, the N_{PC} used in the input layer of the secondary model should be considered. When fewer N_{PC} are needed as input for the secondary model, it indicates the base-model was more effective at extracting information from the image data (Ueda & Hoshiai, 1997). Furthermore, a secondary model which achieves a high AUC using few N_{PC} can be considered to be effective and efficient, balancing performance with simplicity and ensuring better generalisation (Lever et al., 2017). The third step is to look at the $N_{hidden_factors}$. In our study, the $N_{hidden_factors}$ are multiplied by the N_{PC} used in the input layer to find the number of

hidden nodes in the hidden layer, following the example of (Larsen et al. 2019). Overfitting is less likely to occur in a network with fewer nodes, i.e. fewer trainable parameters (Panchal et al., 2011). A secondary model which reaches a high AUC using a lower $N_{\text{hidden_factor}}$ is considered to be superior to a secondary model using a higher $N_{\text{hidden_factor}}$, all else being equal. That being said, a secondary model with too few trainable parameters may be prone to underfitting, where the model will never be able to learn the complex relationship between input and output (Ortega et al., 2018). The optimisation of the secondary model becomes a balancing act to avoid underfitting and overfitting simultaneously.

When examining the two base-models with the highest best AUC values of 0.99, namely *Xception* and *DenseNet201*, they use different N_{PC} in the input layers. *DenseNet201* uses fewer N_{PC} , only 128, whereas *Xception* uses 2499 N_{PC} . This finding suggests that *DenseNet201*, despite its simplicity, can yield the same high performance as *Xception*. This is promising news for real-world applications, indicating that computational efficiency can be achieved without compromising accuracy. However, Table 8 shows us that the best secondary models produced by *Xception* with N_{PC} of 512, 256, 128, and 64 are not significantly worse than the superior one using 2499 N_{PC} . *DenseNet201* already uses fewer N_{PC} , it is not significantly worse using 64 and 32. *EfficientNetB7* and *InceptionResNet_V2* both have slightly lower AUCs of 0.96 and 0.97. However, they only use 64 N_{PC} as input. This further supports the practicality of our findings, as these models demonstrate that high performance can be achieved with minimal complexity. *Resnet101V2* and *MobileNetV2* perform with a best AUC value of 0.98, close to the best AUCs. *MobileNetV2* achieved this performance with 256 N_{PC} . *Resnet101V2*, contrary, uses 10782 N_{PC} . This drastically increases the number of trainable parameters and amplifies the risk of overfitting. However, as shown in Table 8, the best secondary models produced by *Resnet101V2* with the N_{PC} of 512, 256, 128, and 64 are not significantly worse.

Figure 4A illustrates that the *VGG16* yields the lowest best AUC value among the seven best secondary models. However, it is important to note that *VGG16* is not significantly different from the other models because its AUC value lies within the 95% CI. The differences in the best AUC values between the models could not be shown to be statistically significant. Having a larger dataset with more horses would enhance the reliability of our estimated AUC values and amplify the significance of the differences. In Figure 4B, it is observed that *VGG16* additionally has the lowest AUC of all the worst AUCs. Again, it's not significantly worse than the other models because its AUC also lies within the 95% CI of the others. Furthermore, it

illustrates that *VGG16*'s 95% CI falls within an AUC of 0.5, which is the limit for when the performance of a model is no better than random guessing (Çorbacıoğlu & Aksel, 2023). This implies that it cannot be rejected that the worst secondary model performs no better than random coincidences. The same is shown with *MobileNetV2*, which 95% CI also lies within the 0.5 limit. *EfficientNetB7* has the best of the worst AUC values of 0.82, meaning that without optimisation of the hyperparameters, it achieves an AUC above 0.80.

Figures 5 and 6 aim to determine if there is a correlation between the best and worst AUC values, respectively, and the parameters, depth, and top-1 accuracy of the seven base-models. Figure 5A shows a statistically significant negative correlation between the best AUC values of the secondary models and the number of parameters of the seven base-models. This is shown when we look at the p-value, which is significant at 0.007, lower than a 5% probability that the observed results occurred by chance. The r^2 value is 0.79, indicating that the parameters account for 79% of the variance in the best AUCs. When comparing with the other graphs in Figure 5B and 5C, there is no correlation between the best AUC values and the models' depth and top-1 accuracy. A low p-value and r^2 value confirm this in both graphs.

In Figure 6, there is a statistically significant positive correlation between the worst AUC values of the secondary models and the top-1 accuracy. The top-1 accuracy refers to the base-model's first prediction of the image classification and correctly identifies the true class. Therefore, the higher the top-1 accuracy for the base-models, the higher the AUC value the secondary model can achieve. The p-value is 0.012, which is significant. The r^2 is 0.75, illustrating that the top-1 accuracy impacts 75% of the variance of the worst AUC value. However, there is no correlation between the worst AUC value and parameters and depth. The p-values and r^2 are low in both graphs. The depth has a slightly higher r^2 value than the parameters.

In this study, we have selected only the base-model with the highest top-1 accuracy from each base-model family. It is important to highlight that *VGG16*, despite having the largest parameter count, is considered the oldest, most primitive, and achieves the worst performance of the base-models examined in this research. It would be intriguing to explore whether this pattern persists when considering all base-models within each family and if the trend can also be seen for the different base-models within each family. This can be pursued in a future study.

To ensure that the best and worst secondary models did not simply learn to recognise whether the images were filmed horizontally or vertically, we estimated the p-values to be compared with the naive model. Table 6 shows that the p-value for sensitivity for the best secondary models is below 5%, which we use as the limit for statistical significance in this study. This means that the best secondary models for all the base-models do not distinguish the images with "pain face" based on how they were filmed.

Conversely, the p-value for specificity for the best secondary models is very high. This is because 10 of 11 (91%) videos with "no pain face" were filmed vertically; therefore, the naive specificity is 91%, almost the same as the base-models' predictions from 90.9% to 100%.

Table 7 shows that the p-value for sensitivity is above 5% for all the worst secondary models except for *ResNet101V2*. This means that it is not statistically significant, and the secondary models may distinguish the images with "pain face" based on how they were filmed. The naive model's sensitivity is 0.45 because 5 of 11 videos with "pain face" were filmed horizontally. As seen in Table 5, this is close to *EfficientNetB7*'s sensitivity of 0.6, which indicates it is likely that it recognises the "pain face" similarly to the naive model. The same occurs for the specificity of the worst secondary models where the p-values are also above 5%. However, as mentioned earlier, 91% of the images with "no pain face" are filmed vertically, and the naive model's specificity is, therefore, 91% and close to the worst secondary models' specificity, especially *EfficientNetB7*.

4.2 Comparison with existing research

The study by Salim et al. (2023) shows that *Xception* and *DenseNet201* have the highest accuracy in recognising fruit for image classification compared with *MobileNetV3-Small* and *ResNet-50*. Our results of recognising pain in horses are consistent with the findings by Salim et al. (2023). This could indicate that *Xception* and *DenseNet201* are generally suitable for image classification in various scenarios. Lo et al. (2019) have also observed that *Xception* scores have slightly higher accuracy than *VGG16* but are much deeper than *VGG16*. *DenseNet201* achieved higher accuracy than *MobileNetV2* in detecting masked or non-masked faces (Dharma Adhinata et al., 2021). In our study, *DenseNet201* only marginally outperformed *MobileNetV2* regarding the best AUC value.

James et al. (2024) compared *VGG16* to *ResNet101* and *MobileNetV2*. James et al. (2024) found that *VGG16* had the highest accuracy of all three base-models, which does not agree with our results.

Lencioni et al. (2021) developed a model based on deep neural networks that could assess pain using scores from the Horse Grimace Scale (HGS) using image data, achieving 88.3% accuracy. The authors randomly assigned 80% of their 3000 images of seven horses, each with one HGS score, to the training set, 10% to the validation set, and 10% to the test set. This approach implies that the trained model has already encountered several images in the test set, indicating that the test set does not consist of entirely new, unseen data. When images are distributed randomly across each set, there is a risk of data leakage (Kapoor & Narayanan, 2023). Therefore, the model might learn to recognise individual horses rather than identifying signs of pain. Data leakage increases the risk of overfitting, potentially leading to significantly overestimated and unreliable performance (Kapoor & Narayanan, 2023). Consequently, the model presented by Lencioni et al. (2021) is not likely to generalise well to other horses beyond the seven used in their study.

To avoid this issue, our secondary models were trained using per-video cross-validation to ensure one video is always reserved as the test set, providing genuinely unseen data as the training set and the test set are fully separated. All images from each video are iteratively used as our test set. From the remaining 21 videos, 20% of the videos are selected for the validation set, with the rest allocated to the training set. This means that when we test the model on a given test set, the models have previously come across that horse only in the opposite condition from the test set (i.e., if the horse expresses pain in the test video, it did not express it in the training video, and vice versa). The 21 non-test videos were stratified per video to prevent data leakage between the training and validation sets. Consequently, images from 4 videos were consistently included in the validation set. Furthermore, to ensure stratification per video, the process involved stratifying by 'class' to maintain an equal representation of each 'class' in the validation set. As a result, the validation set consistently contained images from two videos featuring “pain face” and two videos with “no pain face”. This design ensures that if our secondary models merely learned to recognise the individual horses, they would consistently make incorrect predictions on the test video. However, the results suggests that the secondary models are effectively learning to distinguish between pain and no-pain facial expressions. Due to this method, we believe our secondary models can be effectively applied to horses not included in our study, demonstrating better generalisability compared to the model in the referenced study. Another limitation of the model proposed by Lencioni et al. (2021) is that it is more likely to overfit when it becomes more complicated with more outputs. Instead of having only two classes of “pain not present” and “pain present” like ours, they used the HGS,

which categorises pain into three levels:” “moderately present,”: “not present”, “moderately present”, and “obviously present” (Lencioni et al., 2021).

HGS and EPF use the same anatomical regions to assess pain (Lencioni et al., 2021). Still, the difference between their study and ours is that HGS examines one image at a time to determine the presence of pain, whereas Gleerup assessed the presence of EPF based on each video in our study.

As EPF is assessed per video sequence rather than per image, it would be advisable to use a technique that can fulfil this requirement. Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) has that exact capability. LSTM models have been used in recent studies to detect tail biting in nursing pigs (Hakansson & Jensen, 2023) and detect piling behaviour in poultry (Jensen et al., 2024). In Hakansson & Jensen (2023), the authors combined *VGG16* in both instances to extract features from videoframes with two LSTM secondary models to analyse sequential data, thereby creating a CNN-LSTM model. The study by Hakansson & Jensen (2023) compared performances with a CNN-CNN model. The results demonstrated that the CNN-LSTM model was superior in generalising to unseen data compared to the CNN-CNN model (Hakansson & Jensen, 2023). In Jensen et al. (2024), the authors compared three secondary models — LSTM, CNN, and FC-ANN — via the pre-trained model *VGG16* to detect piling behaviour automatically. The results indicated that LSTM was considered the best of the three models (Jensen et al., 2024).

While it would be logical to pursue further optimisation with the LSTM models due to the results of the previous studies, our current results exhibit exceptional performance in classifying “pain face” versus “no pain face”. Consequently, additional optimisation with the LSTM secondary models may not be required.

4.3 Limitations

The videos used in this study vary in length from 9.96 to 30.96 seconds and how they are filmed. Six videos were filmed horizontally, while the 16 remaining videos were filmed vertically. It would have been preferable if all the videos had been filmed similarly to create a more uniform dataset. We learned that our secondary models are robust to filming direction as long as the videos are cropped to the same dimensions as the vertically filmed videos, so the horse's face is always centred. In the future, one could imagine that users of the final tool would only need to film vertically, allowing the cropping to be easily automated. When filmed

vertically, it can reduce unnecessary background noise. A uniform video length of 30 seconds would provide more images, resulting in a larger dataset divided into larger training, validation training-, validation-, and test sets.

The overall quality of the videos exhibits considerable variability, showing shaky filming, horses' heads moving away from the frame, and other objects like humans in the videos. To address this, we had to remove 15 unclear and/or disturbed images (10 of which were from a single video) before encoding our dataset. This and the different lengths of the videos result in unbalanced data prior to data augmentation and data balancing with undersampling. The dataset consisted of 316 images of “pain face” and 297 of “no pain face” before data augmentation undersampling.

The dataset's size is also a limitation. Suppose the dataset consisted of more videos of more horses, the sample size increases, providing greater statistical power to detect differences between the secondary models. We would be able to detect whether instances of borderline significance in Tables 6, 7, and 8 are, in fact, significant differences or not. On the other hand, a larger dataset would require longer encoding- and training times, which leads to another limitation of our study.

Due to our computer's capacity constraints, considerable time was required to encode our dataset with the base-models. While we anticipated that the base-models with the most parameters would require the longest encoding times, it was the deeper base-models that resulted in the longest encoding and training times. For instance, *VGG16*, which has the most parameters but a depth of only 16 layers, was the quickest to encode when training the secondary models, in contrast to the deepest model, *Inception_ResNet_V2*, which took the longest and has a depth of 449 layers. We were able to encode the data for all the base-models. The data frames essential to encode our dataset require substantial memory, featuring several hundred thousand attributes for some base-models. The challenge was not storing these data frames in memory but performing operations on them, such as the matrix operations involved in the PCA. Our working memory was exhausted, especially with the deep base models, meaning we could not run PCA or train *DenseNet201*, *EfficientNetB7*, and *Inception_ResNet_V2* on our computers. We were able to borrow another computer to run those models. It was time-consuming to transfer files back and forth for training and then conduct the statistical analysis, causing delays in our data processing. This experience highlights the

importance of considering both the computational capacity and the time requirements when training deep models.

Different scenarios come into play when choosing the most suitable pre-trained CNN base-model. If unlimited computer capacity is available without a specific time limit, *DenseNet201*, *InceptionResNetV2*, and *EfficientNetV2* would be optimal base models due to their high AUC performance, low N_{PC} , and consequently low trainable parameters. Their ability to perform well with a simpler network structure makes them highly practical for real-world applications where resources are constrained. Although *EfficientNetV2* scored a lower best AUC than *DenseNet201* and *InceptionResNetV2*, it is not significantly worse. The worst secondary model extracted from *EfficientNetV2* achieved a high AUC value, which means it might not be necessary to optimise the hyperparameters to achieve a high-performing model.

If limited computer capacity is present, as with the computer used in this study, *VGG16*, *MobileNetV2*, and *Xception* would be optimal pre-trained base-models. They have a short encoding time and still score high AUC performance. *Xception* has a high N_{PC} , despite that it does not significantly impact the AUC value. When looking at the worst performances of the secondary models extracted from *VGG16* and *MobileNetV2*, it is essential to keep in mind that the AUC value of 0.5 lies within the 95% CI, which is not significantly better than random guessing. Therefore, with both *VGG16* and *MobileNetV2*, optimising the hyperparameters should be considered to achieve better performances.

Conclusion

In this study aimed at detecting the Equine Pain Face (EPF) in images of horses, we evaluated the performance of seven pre-trained artificial intelligence base-models with variations in hyperparameters, principal components, and hidden factors. The base-models used were *VGG16*, *Xception*, *DenseNet201*, *ResNet101V2*, *MobileNetV2*, *InceptionResNetV2*.

The results demonstrate that all secondary models produced from the seven base-models performed well, with AUC values from 0.95 to 0.99, suitable for image classification. *DenseNet201* excelled with an AUC of 0.99 and low complexity, requiring only 128 Npc. Despite this, the performance differences between *DenseNet201* and the other models were not significant.

Selecting the most suitable model for classification of horse images in EPF evaluation depends on computational resources and time limitations. *DenseNet201* is recommended if the computer capacity is unlimited. Alternatively, *VGG16* is suitable for limited capacity, offering quicker encoding and high AUC performance. However, for optimal performance, hyperparameters should be optimised.

Perspectives

With further research, AI would make an excellent tool for detecting pain faces in horses. This tool would be available for horse owners and veterinarians in everyday life, especially at competitions. Fédération Equestre Internationale's (FEI) Code of Conduct for the Welfare of the Horse states that the tack must be fitted to avoid the risk of pain or injury (FEI, 2024). Furthermore, it describes how the training methods should match the horses' physical capabilities and level of maturity for their respective disciplines and how abusing a horse with misusing aids (whip, spurs, etc.) would not be tolerated (FEI, 2024) since it can affect the welfare of the horse and result in pain behaviour (Dyson et al., 2018). If AI were implemented as a tool for veterinarians in competitions, it would be possible to detect pain already at the vet check, and it would be possible to declare a horse unfit to compete because of the detection of pain with or without further examination in the Holding Box Examination. This would be a great improvement and assurance of welfare among competition horses.

This tool would be useful for horses in everyday life and stable environments. It would help horse owners detect pain in their horses and seek timely veterinary assistance (Hamilton et al., 2022). This could reduce misinterpretation between conflict behaviour and pain behaviour, promoting the welfare and health of the horses.

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